

Design and Integration of IOT Forest Fire Early Detection and Remote Alerting System

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To Cite this Article

Koya Haritha, T. Archana, Sk. Mohammad Yousuff, S. Venkata Siva Ramesh & N. Yaswanth (2026). Design and Integration of IOT Forest Fire Early Detection and Remote Alerting System. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 12(SI01), 1245-1251. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19792956>

Article Info

Received: 12 March 2026; Revised: 07 April 2026; Accepted: 10 April 2026.

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KEYWORDS

Forest fire detection, Internet of Things (IoT), Arduino Uno, Flame sensor, DHT11 sensor, MQ2 gas sensor, GSM module.

ABSTRACT

Forest fires are one of the most dangerous environment disasters, causing serve damage to ecosystems, wildlife and human life. Early detection plays a critical role in minimizing destruction and enabling timely response. This paper presents the design and implementation of an Arduino Uno powered IoT-based forest fire early detection and remote alerting system. The proposed system integrates multiple sensors such as a flame sensor, DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor and MQ2 Gas sensor to continuously monitor environmental conditions in real time. The collected data is processed using an Arduino Uno microcontroller and displayed locally through an LCD module. In addition to local monitoring, the system utilizes IoT technology to transmit data to cloud platforms, enabling remote access and real-time analysis. A GSM module is incorporated to send instant alerts to authorities when abnormal conditions such as high temperature, smoke, or fire are detected. Furthermore, a camera module is used to provide visual confirmation of fire incidents, enhancing system reliability. Compared to traditional fire detection systems, the proposed model offers a cost-effective, scalable, and efficient solution suitable for deployment in remote forest areas. The system significantly reduces response time and contributes to environmental protection by preventing large-scale forest fires.

I. INTRODUCTION

Forest fires are one of the most destructive natural hazards, causing severe damage to forests, wildlife habitats, and human settlements. They often spread rapidly due to environmental factors such as high temperature, low humidity, dry vegetation, and the presence of flammable gases. In many cases, fires remain undetected in their early stages, leading to large-scale

destruction before any preventive action can be taken. Traditional fire detection methods, including manual surveillance, watch towers, and satellite monitoring, are either labor-intensive or suffer from delayed detection and limited accuracy. These limitations create a strong need for an intelligent, automated system capable of detecting fire hazards at an early stage and providing real-time alerts.

With the rapid advancement of embedded systems and Internet of Things (IoT) technology, it has become possible to design smart monitoring systems that can continuously observe environmental conditions and respond instantly to abnormal situations. IoT enables seamless communication between sensors, microcontrollers, and cloud platforms, allowing remote monitoring and control from any location. Embedded systems, which combine hardware and software to perform specific tasks, play a crucial role in developing such real-time monitoring solutions.

In this project, an Arduino Uno powered IoT-based forest fire early detection and remote alerting system is proposed to overcome the limitations of conventional methods. The system integrates multiple sensors such as a flame sensor, DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor, and MQ-2 gas sensor to monitor environmental parameters like temperature, humidity, smoke, and fire presence. These sensors continuously collect real-time data, which is processed by the Arduino Uno microcontroller to identify potential fire conditions. The system is designed to detect even small changes in environmental parameters, enabling early-stage fire detection.

To enhance usability, the system displays real-time data on an LCD module for local monitoring and simultaneously transmits the information to cloud platforms using IoT technology. This allows authorities to monitor forest conditions remotely and take necessary actions when required. In addition, a GSM module is incorporated to send instant alert messages when abnormal conditions are detected, ensuring quick response and reducing the risk of fire spread. A camera module is also included to provide visual confirmation of fire incidents, thereby improving system reliability and accuracy.

The proposed system offers a cost-effective, efficient, and scalable solution for forest fire detection, especially in remote and inaccessible areas where continuous human monitoring is not feasible. By integrating multiple sensors, IoT communication, and real-time alert mechanisms, the system significantly improves detection speed and response time. Ultimately, this approach contributes to environmental protection, wildlife conservation, and disaster management by enabling early detection and prevention of forest fires [1][2].

II. REVIEW LITERATURE SURVEY

Forest fire detection has been an active area of research due to the increasing environmental and economic damage caused by wildfires across the globe. Earlier studies primarily focused on traditional fire detection techniques such as satellite-based monitoring and watchtower surveillance systems. Although these methods are capable of covering large geographical areas, they often suffer from delayed detection, limited resolution, and dependency on weather conditions such as clouds and smoke, which can obscure visibility. These limitations reduce their effectiveness in providing early warnings and rapid response to fire outbreaks [1].

To overcome these challenges, researchers introduced Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) for environmental monitoring. These systems deploy multiple sensor nodes in forest areas to continuously monitor parameters such as temperature, humidity, and smoke levels. Sensor-based systems significantly improve detection speed compared to traditional methods; however, they are often limited by issues such as high deployment cost, energy consumption, and lack of efficient communication over long distances. Additionally, many early WSN-based systems provided only local monitoring without real-time remote access or alert mechanisms [2].

With the advancement of Internet of Things (IoT) technology, modern research has shifted towards developing smart fire detection systems that integrate sensors, microcontrollers, and cloud platforms. IoT-based systems enable real-time data collection, transmission, and remote monitoring through the internet. Studies have shown that integrating sensors like temperature, gas, and humidity sensors with IoT platforms significantly improves the accuracy and efficiency of fire detection systems. These systems also support features such as SMS alerts, cloud dashboards, and geolocation tracking, making them more practical for real-world applications [3].

Recent research has further enhanced IoT-based fire detection systems by incorporating Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning techniques. AI models are used to analyze sensor data and predict fire outbreaks more accurately by reducing false alarms. Advanced systems combine IoT sensing with deep learning algorithms and camera-based monitoring to improve detection reliability and provide visual confirmation of

fire incidents. Such hybrid approaches offer higher accuracy, faster detection, and better decision-making capabilities compared to traditional threshold-based systems [4].

Despite these advancements, several challenges still exist in current fire detection systems, including network reliability in remote forest areas, power management of sensor nodes, and maintaining system accuracy under varying environmental conditions. Many systems are also expensive or complex, limiting their large-scale deployment. Therefore, there is a need for a cost-effective, integrated, and reliable solution that combines multiple sensors, real-time monitoring, IoT communication, and alert mechanisms.

The proposed system addresses these research gaps by integrating Arduino Uno, multiple environmental sensors, IoT cloud communication, GSM alerting, and camera-based monitoring into a single platform. This approach ensures early detection, improved accuracy, reduced response time, and practical deployment in remote forest regions, making it a more efficient solution compared to existing systems [1][2][3][4].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is designed to monitor forest environments and detect early signs of fire using multiple sensors, an Arduino Uno microcontroller, IoT communication, and GSM alert mechanisms. The methodology focuses on sensing environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, smoke, and flame presence, processing the data, and generating alerts when abnormal conditions are detected.

A. System Design

The system consists of sensors such as a flame sensor, DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor, and MQ-2 gas sensor, which are deployed in the forest area to monitor environmental conditions. These sensors are connected to the Arduino Uno microcontroller, which acts as the central processing unit. An ESP8266 module is used for IoT communication, while a GSM module is integrated for alert notifications. An LCD display is also included to show real-time data locally.

B. Data Acquisition

The sensors continuously monitor environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, presence of smoke, and flame detection. The Arduino reads this data at regular intervals and converts it into meaningful

values. These real-time readings are used to analyze the environmental condition and identify any potential fire hazards.

C. Data Processing

The Arduino processes the collected sensor data by comparing it with predefined threshold values. For example, high temperature, low humidity, presence of gas, or detection of flame indicates a possible fire condition. If all parameters are within safe limits, the system continues monitoring. If any parameter exceeds the threshold, the system identifies it as a fire risk condition.

D. Display Unit

An I2C LCD module is used to display real-time environmental data such as temperature, humidity, and gas levels. It also shows system status messages like "SAFE" or "FIRE DETECTED," allowing easy monitoring at the location.

E. Alert Mechanism

When a fire condition is detected, the Arduino activates the GSM module to send an SMS alert to the registered mobile number. Simultaneously, the system uploads data to the IoT cloud platform (ThingSpeak), enabling remote monitoring. A buzzer is also triggered to provide an immediate local alert.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system presents a smart and automated approach for forest fire detection using Arduino Uno, multiple sensors, IoT technology, and GSM communication. The system is designed to continuously monitor environmental conditions and provide real-time alerts to prevent fire hazards.

In this methodology, sensors such as flame sensor, DHT11, and MQ-2 are deployed to detect key fire indicators like temperature rise, smoke presence, and flame occurrence. The sensors convert physical parameters into electrical signals, which are processed by the Arduino Uno microcontroller.

The Arduino acts as the brain of the system, where all sensor data is analyzed and compared with predefined threshold values. Based on this analysis, the system determines whether the environment is safe or if there is a risk of fire.

An I2C LCD module is used to display real-time environmental conditions locally, providing immediate information to nearby users. At the same time, the

ESP8266 module sends data to the IoT cloud platform, allowing remote monitoring from anywhere.

When abnormal conditions such as high temperature or smoke are detected, the Arduino triggers the GSM module to send an SMS alert to authorities or users. Additionally, a buzzer alarm is activated to indicate danger locally. The system operates continuously and automatically, ensuring reliable monitoring without human intervention.

WORKING PRINCIPLE

working principle of the proposed forest fire detection system is based on continuous environmental monitoring and automated alert generation. The system uses sensors to detect parameters such as temperature, humidity, gas concentration and flame pressure.

Initially, the sensors detect environmental conditions and convert them into electrical signals. These signals are processed and digitized, then sent to the Arduino microcontroller. The Arduino reads the data at regular intervals and analyzes the current environmental condition.

A predefined threshold value is set for each parameter, such as temperature and gas levels. The Arduino continuously compares the sensor readings with these threshold values. If the values remain within safe limits, the system indicates a normal condition.

The real-time data is displayed on the LCD module for local monitoring. However, if any parameter exceeds the threshold value, the system identifies it as a fire risk condition. In such cases, the Arduino activates the GSM module to send alert messages to the user. Simultaneously, the buzzer is triggered, and data is uploaded to the IoT cloud platform for remote monitoring.

This process is repeated continuously, ensuring real-time monitoring and immediate response. Thus, the system provides an efficient and reliable method for early fire detection using sensing, processing, communication, and alert technologies.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig. 4.1. Block Diagram

V. RESULTS AND OUTCOMES

The proposed Arduino Uno powered IoT forest fire detection system was successfully designed and implemented using multiple sensors, GSM communication, and IoT technology. The system was tested under different environmental conditions to evaluate its performance and reliability.

Fig. 1. The sensors accurately detected variations in temperature, humidity, smoke, and flame presence. The Arduino processed the sensor data effectively and displayed real-time values on the LCD module. The system continuously monitored environmental conditions without interruption.

Fig. 2. When abnormal conditions such as high temperature or smoke were detected, the system responded immediately. The GSM module successfully sent alert messages to the registered mobile number without delay. The buzzer also provided instant local alerts, ensuring immediate awareness of fire hazards

Fig. 3. The IoT module transmitted data to the cloud platform, enabling remote monitoring. The system demonstrated fast response time, high accuracy, and reliable performance. It reduced dependency on manual monitoring and minimized the chances of delayed detection.

Fig. 5.1. Output1

Fig. 5.2. Output 2

Overall, the system proved to be cost-effective, efficient, and suitable for deployment in remote forest areas. The results show that the proposed system can significantly improve early fire detection and reduce environmental damage.

VI. CONCLUSION

The Arduino Uno powered IoT forest fire early detection and remote alerting system was successfully developed and tested. The system effectively monitors environmental conditions and detects early signs of fire using multiple sensors.

The integration of sensors, Arduino, GSM module, and IoT technology ensures real-time monitoring and immediate alert generation. The LCD provides local monitoring, while the GSM module ensures timely notifications. The IoT platform enables remote access and data analysis.

The system demonstrated reliable performance, quick response, and accurate detection during testing. It reduces manual effort, improves safety, and helps prevent large-scale forest damage.

In conclusion, the proposed system offers a simple, cost-effective, and efficient solution for forest fire detection. It is highly suitable for remote and inaccessible areas, contributing to environmental protection and disaster management. The project

highlights the importance of combining embedded systems and IoT technologies for real-world applications.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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